

Interval Measurement Versus a Continuous Variable in Quantum Entropy Calculations Part II

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In Part I, we argued that $P(x)dx$ is based on the partitioning of a length L into dx pieces and assigning these a probability. A moving object, however, is in continuous motion and should be described by a continuous x . If one wishes to measure the position of a particle moving with constant v , one would partition a length L into dx pieces and find the probability of the particle being in dx . This seems to have physical meaning as it is directly linked to a measurement. There is always some uncertainty in a measurement hit at an x , and so one has the notion of a dx .

An interaction, however, occurs at various x points whether one measures it or not. As a result, one does not need a dx interval. We argue that this is why it is an approximation, or even incorrect, to state that there is a probability for a particle with constant p to be in a dx and for each dx , it may impart an impulse proportional to p . This is a quasi-static picture in which the particle is moved from one dx to another. A moving particle is instead a dynamic object and this is part of the meaning of p . We argue it is not fully accurate to consider interval based motion separated from p , i.e. state that there is a probability to be in dx and then associate this with p . Rather, we suggest that one requires continuous motion in x linked with p . This suggests periodic motion, we argue, and we suggest a picture of rotation as an a priori model, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Such a quantity is completely at odds with the picture of a particle in dx having an impulse proportional to p .

$\exp(ipx)$ has two important features. First, it is not associated with any imposed dx and secondly, it contains its own inherent length, \hbar/p which is called a wavelength. The fact that it is complex describes it as dynamic object. An issue which arises, however, is that if one wishes to measure a particle in dx , one cannot directly use $\exp(ipx)$. It is associated with each x point, with no dx error, and so describes interactions which are not being followed by measurements at each dx , i.e. one does not follow a particle in time, $x(t)$. Nevertheless, $\exp(ipx)$ must somehow map into the $P(x,p)dx=dx/L$ picture for the sake of measurement. Such a picture contains no information about p and so one must remove p and obtain a constant. This occurs mathematically through $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$.

The point we wish to stress is that impulses occur through momentum, but momentum is directly linked with motion and so one needs a strictly dynamic picture in x and p . One does not need to follow a particle in time because $p=mv_1=mv_2$ yield the same impulse, so this is not dynamics in time, but in x and p . Measurements which use dx are somewhat static in nature, and although they are physical, are not directly associated with the dynamics which occurs. Thus, the static picture of p in each dx does not properly capture full dynamics, we argue. In other words, the fact that one does not measure each instant $x(t)$ does not mean that an interaction is not going to occur in x . $\exp(ipx)$ is a function which is not associated with instantaneous measurements (i.e. one does not determine which slit a particle passes through), but it is associated with a wavelength which means that there can be interfering probabilities in space (dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$ to pass through one slit or the other. In this sense, $\exp(ipx)$ acts like a probability. It is the dynamic probability which leads to average kinetic energy in a single particle bound state, but if one wishes to go back to a measurement picture, one needs to take $P(x)dx = W^*(x)W(x)dx$, to find a static spatial density and multiply this by the average kinetic energy at x , based on a dynamic average using $\exp(ipx)$.

Interval Measurement

As noted in part I, intervals are associated with measurement and are fundamental in Newtonian mechanics. For example, speed is dx/dt . The idea is to allow the interval to shrink to 0, but in terms of measurements, this is not possible because there is some nonzero dx and dt error. Thus, we link intervals to measurements and insist that they cannot become zero.

The point we wish to make, however, is that one does not have to measure a particle at each x,t point as is done in classical mechanics. Furthermore, as pointed in Part I, even classical

probabilistic scenarios use intervals. For example, for a bound classical particle, probability to be in dx (an interval) is proportional to dt , (another interval) so that;

$$P(x,v) dx = C dx/v(x) \quad ((1-A)) \quad \text{For } v=\text{constant}, \quad P(x,v)dx=cx/L \quad ((1-B))$$

The interval picture suggests that if one wishes to think of the impact of a moving particle, one considers its probability to be in an interval dx and then associates with it an impulse proportional to p . In the case of pressure, one also considers a flux, i.e. a frequency in time.

Impulse of Single Particle

As noted above, the interval picture associates $P(x,p)dx=dx/L$ with an impulse proportional to p . Given that $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ and that one is interested only in impulses, one need not consider motion in time because this is associated with velocity and not impulse. We argue that the static picture which uses an interval probability $P(x,p)dx$ together with p cannot be fully correct because one does not have to make measurements to ensure a particle is one dx or another in order for it to interact. It interacts without measurements, i.e. without an interval picture. In fact, we suggested in Part I that it should be described by a continuous x variable and p for impulse. Furthermore, a particle with constant p is moving and so it seems one really needs a dynamic and not quasi-static interval picture. A real distribution, however, is a static picture. One needs at least two dimensions to describe dynamics and the simplest picture seems to be cycling, i.e.

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

$((2))$ seems to have several fundamental features. First, it is complex because it is dynamic and a real function is static. Second, it is not associated with an imposed dx from measurement and third, it contains its own length \hbar/p , called a wavelength. The last feature is critical because it means that there is uncertainty in x for a given p based on \hbar/p . In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is probabilistic. In the interval approach, uncertainty is based on measurement uncertainty dx which has nothing to do with lengths in potentials in the real world, i.e. single slit diffraction or 2-slit interference etc. The cycling, dynamic picture, suggests different interfering $\exp(ipx)$ type terms resulting from say two slit interference, one for each slit. This has the form of an OR probability addition, but one may only consider it as a priori two cyclings with different p angles (same magnitude). The key is that $\exp(ipx)$ is sensitive to lengths in nature of the order of \hbar/p , and this in turn follows from the fact that it is cyclical.

This still leaves an important question unanswered. Spatial measurements are based on a dx interval approach, but such a picture is inadequate to describe interactions of dynamic particle which must be described using $((2))$, we argue. Once one has obtained a sum of interfering $\exp(ipx)$ s, one has a complex (or even real if $a(p)=+/-a(-p)$, $a(p)$ being a weight of $\exp(ipx)$) function. This function is in x , however, so how is it linked with $P(x)dx$ which must exist in the dx measurement scenario?

We argued above that $\exp(ipx)$ maps into $P(x,p)dx=dx/L$ by removing p information, i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. We suggest that this recipe be extended to $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ i.e.

$$P(x)dx = W^*(x)W(x)dx \quad ((3))$$

In other words, a dynamic function $\exp(ipx)$ which describes interactions at any x without any sense of an imposed dx maps into a $P(x)$ which requires an imposed dx because it is associated with measurement. Thus, measurement in quantum mechanics is associated with $P(x)dx$ and not with an actual physical interaction which occurs. Furthermore, in $\exp(ipx)$ one has p , momentum, which presumably may be measured. This p may exist at any x point due to the periodicity of $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, if one speaks of the probability of p (in the sense of what may be measured), one cannot

know what x point is involved, i.e. $P(p)dp = a^*(p)a(p) dp$, even though an interaction occurs through the dynamic $\exp(ipx)$ which holds for a known, but not measured value, of p and x .

As a result, quantum mechanics operates dynamically at a non-measured level which uses a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ or $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but physically one must make measurements which forces one back into the interval world $P(x)dx=W^*(x)W(x)dx$ and $P(p)dp=a^*(p)a(p)$.

For example, if one considers a quantum single particle bound state, a particle interacts with a potential $V(x)$. This requires the dynamic $\exp(ipx)$ picture. For the two slit scenario one considers interactions with each slit leading to $\exp(i p_1 \text{ dot } r) + \exp(i p_2 \text{ dot } r)$ where $\text{magnitude}(p_1) = \text{magnitude}(p_2)$. The weights of each is the same because there is no bias, i.e. one has no idea through which slit the particle passed. The two different $\exp(ip \text{ dot } r)$ terms interfere at the same r points. The same scenario seems to hold for a bound state. Various $\exp(ipx)$ terms may be stirred up by the potential and these interfere at all x points leading to the profile $W(x)= \text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but here $a(p)$ values are not known a priori. One needs to go one step further and suggest that the a priori $\exp(ipx)$ behaves like a probability. In other words, average kinetic energy is given by:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)) \quad ((4))$$

This, we argue, is an interesting result because it suggests that if one wishes to measure average kinetic energy in a system, one does need to convert $KE(ave)$ itself into an interval quantity. Rather, it is multiplied by an interval quantity, namely $W^*(x)W(x)dx$. In other words, $KE(x)$ is an intrinsic dynamic quantity which is multiplied by density which depends on dx . This approach is analogous to an average single particle pressure being multiplied by density at x in classical statistical mechanics.

To see that $\exp(ipx)$ acts like a probability, one may note that it is associated with an uncertainty in length of \hbar/p . If two different potential pieces, i.e. two slits, exist within this length, one cannot be sure with which one the particle interacts. This is a probabilistic scenario. Thus, it seems that one is justified in using $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, even though it is complex and $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ may take on negative values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that an interval picture, i.e. one using dx for example, is required for measurement because there are always errors in determining x . Thus, one has $P(x)dx$. If one takes this picture seriously, then a particle with p has a probability to be in dx and it will render an impulse proportional to p . This, however, removes all dynamics associated with continuous motion in x , which is what occurs for a moving particle. We consider p , not v , because we are interested in impulse and are not measuring the particle as it moves in space and time. A particle with constant p should exhibit continuous motion in x and should not be constrained by a measurement dx . As a result, we suggest one may introduce a priori a two dimensional p,x function, because a one dimensional one is static. The simplest is a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$. This suggests directly that one is not measuring what is happening at each dx , but rather has dynamic function, not tied to dx , which has its own length \hbar/p . This means there is uncertainty in x for a given p which manifests itself, for example, in 2 slit interference. One may have $\exp(ipx)$ for each slit, i.e. $\exp(ip_1 \text{ dot } r) + \exp(ip_2 \text{ dot } r)$ with $\text{magnitude}(p_1)=\text{magnitude}(p_2)$. In other words, the interaction occurs without one classically following it in space as such a following means a static dx interval picture which is not dynamic.

Ultimately, however, a measurement must occur. How does one link $\exp(ipx)$ to a measurement which requires a dx ? We suggest that given that $P(x,p)dx=dx/L$, $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ maps to $P(x,p)$. Thus, one may carry out calculations using the dynamic $\exp(ipx)$, but after a final $W(x)=\text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, one needs to use $W^*(x)W(x)$ to return to the world of measurement. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is dynamic and describes dynamic interactions not based on any dx by dx measurement.

Only the final outcome is measured using dx intervals. $\exp(ipx)$ is probabilistic in the sense that there is a characteristic length \hbar/p and one does not know if the particle interacts with one slit or the other if they exist within in this length range. Thus, one treats the problem probabilistic considering $\exp(ipx)$ for interactions with each slit.